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Diffraction of Light

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1 Introduction

Experimentally, it has been observed that light has properties of both particles and waves. This phenomenon is called wave-particle duality. The wave properties of light become apparent, for example, in slit experiments, where light passes through one (or more) very narrow slits. In such cases, it is observed that instead of a single bright region, several distinct bright regions are formed on the other side of the obstacle.

In this laboratory exercise, the properties of the wave nature of light were investigated. The aim of the work was to make observations of the behavior of light waves using single-slit and double-slit experiments, and to determine the mathematical properties of phenomena related to the wave nature of light, such as interference and diffraction. Based on the results, the size of the used slits/gratings is evaluated. In general, mathematical models of light waves can be utilized, for example, in experimental studies of different materials or the properties of light.

Studying the wave nature of light involves several challenges that make obtaining accurate measurement results difficult. The difficulty of experimental investigations is largely due to the very small scale of light waves, since the order of magnitude of the wavelength of visible light is 100nm. Due to this small order of magnitude, accurately determining both the properties of light and the size of the gratings used in slit experiments is challenging.

In this laboratory work, modern computer-based measurement equipment is utilized, which collects light intensity and position data with high precision. In addition, the properties of the light source and gratings used in the experiment are known with good accuracy. These facilitate the collection of accurate data and minimize errors.

2 Abstract

The work investigated the properties of the wave nature of light using single-slit and double-slit experiments. In the single-slit experiment, a diffraction pattern was observed, whereas in the double-slit experiment an interference pattern occurred. The results confirmed the manifestation of the wave nature of light through diffraction and interference phenomena.

3 Model and Methods

3.1 Huygens' Principle and Interference

Investigating the wave nature of light using slit experiments is based on **Huygens'** principle. According to Huygens' principle, a wavefront is formed by individual oscillators that independently act as sources of spherical waves. Upon encountering a slit/grating, only a very small part of the light wavefront passes through the slit. These act as sources of a new spherical wave on the other side of the slit, forming a new curved wavefront. [1] This is illustrated in Figure 1, where the red lines represent the peaks of the wavefront, and the blue lines represent the direction of propagation.

Figure 1: Bending of the wavefront upon encountering a slit

Interference is a phenomenon in which two or more waves meet and interact with each other. When two or more waves meet, a resultant wave is formed, whose magnitude is obtained by the principle of superposition, i.e., by summing the displacements of the waves at each point in space. Interference is an essential phenomenon for the experiment, since it affects both the single-slit and double-slit cases and leads to the observed results. [1]

Interference is constructive if the waves reinforce each other, and destructive if the waves weaken each other. When the waves arrive at the same point in the same phase, as in Figure 2, a maximum of constructive interference is formed. At a point where the phase difference of the waves is exactly half a wavelength, the waves cancel each other completely. [1]

Figure 2: Constructive interference

Based on this, an equation can be written for the location where constructive interference occurs (assuming that the light sources emit light in the same phase):

$$r_2 - r_1 = n\lambda \quad (n = 0, 1, 2, 3 \dots) \quad (1)$$

Where r_1, r_2 are the positions of the sources, n is the order of the intensity maximum, and λ is the wavelength. Similarly, an equation for destructive interference is obtained:

$$r_2 - r_1 = (n + 1/2)\lambda \quad (n = 0, 1, 2, 3 \dots) \quad (2)$$

In the case of a double-slit experiment, this equation can be expressed in terms of the distance between the slits and the angles of the intensity maxima formed on the screen. The equation assumes that the slit separation is so small relative to the distance to the screen that the rays can be approximated as parallel, as illustrated in Figure 3:

Figure 3: Interference in the case of a double slit (not to scale)

Using this approximation, equation (1) can be rewritten in the form:

$$d \sin(\theta) = n\lambda \quad (n = 0, 1, 2, 3 \dots) \quad (3)$$

Where d is the distance between the slits and θ is the deviation from the incident direction of the light ray. This equation can thus be used to determine the intensity maxima of the diffraction pattern. [1]

3.2 Diffraction

In addition to interference, the laboratory experiment investigates the **diffraction** of light. Diffraction is a phenomenon in which light bends (according to Huygens' principle) around an obstacle it encounters, as seen in Figure 1. In the case of a single slit, the spherical-wave elements passing through the slit interfere with each other and create a diffraction pattern behind the slit. [1]

Figure 4: Diffraction with a single slit

Figure 4 presents a model for diffraction from a single slit. Here the same approximation is made as in the double-slit experiment, i.e., it is assumed that the light rays are parallel. The difference, however, is that an intensity minimum is formed at the path difference $D \sin(\theta)$. This is because for a phase difference of one full wavelength, for every ray in between there exists a counterpart with a half-wavelength phase difference (visible in the figure as rays of the same color), meaning that the rays cancel completely. [1]

From this, the equation for the positions of the intensity minima of the diffraction pattern is obtained:

$$D \sin(\theta) = m\lambda \quad (n = 0, 1, 2, 3 \dots) \quad (4)$$

Here D is the slit width and m is the order of the intensity minimum.

3.3 Position Functions of Intensity Minima/Maxima

One of the objectives of the measurement is to determine the positions of intensity minima and maxima as a function of their order. The slit widths used in the measurement are significantly larger than the wavelength λ , so (based on equations (3) and (4)) it is known that the angle θ is very small.

Thus, the approximation $\sin(\theta) = y/R$ can be used. Substituting this into equations (3) and (4) and solving for the distance y yields the following equations [2]:

$$y_n = \frac{R\lambda}{d}n \quad (5)$$

$$y_m = \frac{R\lambda}{D}m \quad (6)$$

Where y_n is the distance of the n th intensity maximum of the interference pattern produced by the double slit from the center of the pattern. Correspondingly, y_m is the distance of the m th intensity minimum of the single-slit diffraction pattern from the center of the pattern.

When the positions of intensity maxima/minima are determined as a function of the order (n/m), they lie on a straight line whose slope is; for a single slit: $k = \frac{R\lambda}{D}$ and for a double slit: $k = \frac{R\lambda}{d}$

These equations are valid only if the light sources of both slits are **coherent**. Coherent light is **monochromatic**, i.e., it consists of only a single wavelength (or a very narrow part of the spectrum), meaning it is completely single-colored. In addition, in coherent light the amplitude and phase difference are the same. The diode laser used in the experiment produces approximately coherent light.

3.4 Measurement Setup

In the laboratory experiment, the diffraction/interference pattern formed on the screen is examined with both one and two slits. Based on the obtained results, conclusions are drawn about the used slit/grating structures. The test setup is shown in Figure 5

Figure 5: Experimental setup and measurement equipment [2]

The components of the measurement apparatus are on a rail, which allows their distance relative to each other to be adjusted and measured. A diode laser is used in the experiment as a source of coherent light. In addition,

a slit holder is used that contains different single and double slits, whose properties are known. The diffraction/interference pattern is projected onto a screen that moves laterally relative to the rail. The screen measures both the light intensity and the lateral position. The sensor measures intensity as a function of position using a computer connected to the apparatus.

This measurement setup was chosen because its physical operation corresponds to the models in Figures 3 and 4, so equations (3) and (4) are valid for the positions of intensity minima and maxima of the light patterns.

Table of initialized measurement parameters:

	Parameter value and uncertainty	Unit
Slit holder position	102 (± 0.2)	cm
Screen position	7 (± 0.2)	cm
Distance between slit and screen (R)	95	cm
Laser wavelength (λ)	635	nm

Table 1: Initialized parameters

4 Results

In the laboratory work, a total of five different measurements were carried out; two measurements with one slit and three measurements with two slits. In each measurement, the slit width and/or separation was changed.

	Slit/Slits width D	Slit separation d
One slit (first measurement)	0.16 mm	-
One slit (second measurement)	0.08 mm	-
Two slits (third measurement)	0.08 mm	0.25 mm
Two slits (fourth measurement)	0.08 mm	0.50 mm
Two slits (fifth measurement)	0.04 mm	0.25 mm

Table 2: Performed measurements

4.1 Diffraction with a Single Slit

In the single-slit measurements, the following results were obtained and plotted. The plots show the light intensity as a function of the (lateral) position of the sensor.

Figure 6: $D=0.08\text{mm}$

Figure 7: $D=0.16\text{mm}$

Figure 8: Diffraction patterns overlaid to scale

From Figure 8 it is observed that when the slit width is increased, the diffraction pattern becomes narrower. The intensity minima(/maxima) of the narrower diffraction pattern are more closely spaced and closer to the center of the pattern.

The observed phenomenon is consistent with previous mathematical models. Based on equation (1), when the slit width is increased (m and λ are constants), the term $\sin(\theta)$ must decrease, i.e., the deviation angle θ of the light decreases. In that case the diffraction pattern narrows, and the diffraction minima shift closer to the center. When the slit width is decreased, the opposite phenomenon occurs, i.e., the diffraction pattern broadens.

In addition, from Figure 8 it can be observed that when the slit width is decreased, the intensity maxima also decrease, especially the central ($n=0$) maximum. This is because such a large amount of light cannot pass through the slit, which reduces the observed intensity. On the other hand, in a narrower slit the diffraction pattern is wider, in which case the peak value of the light intensity is smaller.

4.2 Interference with Two Slits

The following measurements were performed with two slits, and their results were plotted. The plots show the light intensity as a function of the (lateral) position of the sensor.

Figure 9: $D=0.08\text{mm}$, $d=0.25\text{mm}$

Figure 10: $D=0.08\text{mm}$, $d=0.5\text{mm}$

Figure 11: $D=0.04\text{mm}$, $d=0.25$

From the double-slit experiments, it is observed that the intensity distribution contains maxima and minima at a considerably denser spacing. In addition, the same phenomenon is observed as in the single-slit case: the diffraction pattern narrows when the slit separation is increased. These phe-

nomena can be justified using equation (3), in the same way as was done for the single-slit case.

4.3 Diffraction with Two Slits

From Figures 9-11 it is observed that the intensity distribution of the double slit contains features arising from both interference and diffraction. The distribution consists of very dense local variation and a larger-scale modulation. With two slits, the pattern is thus affected by the diffraction from the individual slits and the interference due to multiple slits. This can be illustrated by overlaying the same plots:

Figure 12: $D=0.08\text{mm}$, $d=0.25\text{mm}$ Figure 13: $D=0.08\text{mm}$, $d=0.25\text{mm}$
 $D=0.08\text{mm}$, $d=0.50\text{mm}$ $D=0.04$, $d=0.25$

From Figure 12 it is observed that the interference pattern is considerably denser when the slit separation is larger ($d=0.5\text{mm}$, dark brown in the figure). On the other hand, the long-term modulation arising from diffraction remains constant. From Figure 13 it is observed that when the slit width is reduced, the diffraction pattern broadens ($D=0.04\text{mm}$, light blue in the figure), while the denser interference pattern remains the same.

From Figures 14 and 15 it is observed (single slit in red and double slits in green) that when the slit widths (D) are identical, the frequency of minima and maxima of the diffraction patterns is the same for both one and two slits. As can be seen from the figures, the slit separation (d) does not change the frequency of the underlying modulation produced by diffraction. The slit separation changes only the interference and the magnitude of the intensity maxima.

4.4 Slit Widths and Separations

Finally, the results are analyzed by determining the positions of the diffraction minima and interference maxima up to third order. These results are

Figure 14: $D=0.08\text{mm}$
 $D=0.08\text{mm}$, $d=0.25\text{mm}$

Figure 15: $D=0.08\text{mm}$,
 $D=0.08$, $d=0.5$

plotted: the position of the diffraction minimum as a function of order m and the position of the interference maximum as a function of order n .

Here the fourth measurement is selected (double slit; $D=0.08\text{mm}$, $d=0.5\text{mm}$):

m	Position of diffraction minimum (mm)
-3	46.8
-2	55.19
-1	63.03
-	-
+1	78.69
+2	86.71
+3	94.11

Table 3: Diffraction minima

Straight lines are fitted to this data and their slopes are determined:

In Figures 16 and 17, the positions of the intensity minima and maxima are presented as functions of their orders. From this, the slopes and their uncertainties are obtained.

n	Position of interference maximum (mm)
-3	67.32
-2	68.62
-1	69.63
0	70.89
+1	72.00
+3	73.29
+3	74.42

Table 4: Diffraction maxima

Figure 16: Positions of diffraction minima as a function of order

Figure 17: Positions of interference maxima as a function of order

Slope: $k_{diffraktio}$ (mm)	7.9 ± 0.0573
Slope: $k_{interferenssi}$ (mm)	1.179 ± 0.0124

Table 5: Slopes

Using equations (5) and (6), the slit width (D) and the slit separation (d) can be determined from the slopes:

$$D = \frac{R\lambda}{y_m} m \quad (7)$$

$$d = \frac{R\lambda}{y_n} n \quad (8)$$

By substituting the values of the slopes and the initialized parameter values (from Table 1), the following results are obtained:

Slit width D (mm)	0.076 ± 0.000393
Slit separation d (mm)	0.512 ± 0.004304

Table 6: Slit width and separation

4.5 Calculation of Measurement Errors

From Table 6 it is observed that the obtained values correspond fairly well to the expected values. The uncertainties of the results were calculated using the total differential, where the uncertainty of the slope and the uncertainty of the distance between the screen and the sensor were used. The total differentials were calculated in equations (9) and (10).

$$\frac{\Delta D}{D} = \frac{k\Delta l - l\Delta k}{kl} \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{\Delta d}{d} = \frac{k\Delta l - l\Delta k}{kl} \quad (10)$$

4.6 Summary and Discussion

In the laboratory work, a diode laser was used as a coherent light source and a slit holder containing various single and double slits. The measurement equipment also included a screen on which light intensity and lateral position were measured using a computer. The measurement setup was chosen so that it corresponded to the physical model for which the associated equations are valid for the positions of intensity minima and maxima of the light patterns. As the mathematical model, the well-known grating equation and its variants were used.

In the experiment, the diffraction pattern produced by a single slit and the interference phenomenon of a double slit were observed. In addition, it was noted that diffraction occurs in both the single- and double-slit experiments. In the case of a double slit, diffraction appears as long-term modulation of the intensity, and interference as very dense local intensity variation. Based on the results, it can be stated that the distribution of the diffraction pattern depends only on the slit width and is not affected by the number of slits or their separation (d). Correspondingly, the slit width (D) has no effect on the distribution of the interference pattern in the double-slit experiment. Thus, equations (3) and (4) can be stated to be generally valid for predicting the position and distribution of diffraction minima and interference maxima.

The obtained results were primarily meaningful, and their accuracy is fairly good. The results correspond to the expected phenomena and support previous theories of the behavior of light. The measured slit width differs by about 4.5% from the stated value (with the largest calculated uncertainty the deviation is 4.0%), but the slit separation differs by only 2.3% (with the largest calculated uncertainty the deviation is 1.4%). From this it can be concluded that the accuracy/uncertainty estimate of the measurement parameters has not been sufficiently accurate. There were also gross errors in the measurement.

Although the results matched expectations, it is important to note that the slit widths used in the experiment were significantly larger than the wavelength of light, which may have affected the accuracy of the results. [3] The work also did not test the results at different wavelengths or with a larger number of slits. Thus, although the results were generalizable to this measurement setup, their general validity in other situations may vary.

In future studies, the experiments could be expanded using different slit and grating structures as well as different light sources. In addition, the manifestation of the wave nature of light under different conditions could be studied in more detail, and it could be determined how different parameters affect diffraction and interference phenomena.

In summary, the laboratory experiment made it possible to illustrate the properties of the wave nature of light through diffraction and interference phenomena. The obtained results were in line with expectations and confirmed well-known theories of the behavior of light.

5 References

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